

WINTER WHEAT VEGETATION

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Abstract

By following the correct technology for winter wheat production and grain storage, high economic efficiency of the activity can be achieved. Winter wheat is one of the crops that has been cultivated for many years, and until now it has deservedly taken the leading place in the ranking of food products in about 50 countries of the world. Uzbekistan is also included in this list and, in addition, it is the main producer and exporter of this cereal crop. This article discusses winter wheat vegetation and its cultivation.

Keywords. Winter wheat vegetation, grain storage, wheat types, mechanism of wheat cultivation.

Аннотация

При соблюдении правильной технологии производства и хранения зерна озимой пшеницы можно добиться высокой экономической эффективности деятельности. Озимая пшеница – одна из культур, которая возделывается уже много лет, и до сих пор заслуженно занимает лидирующие места в рейтингах продуктов питания примерно в 50 странах мира. Узбекистан также входит в этот список и, кроме того, является основным производителем и экспортером этой зерновой культуры. В данной статье рассматривается вегетация озимой пшеницы и ее возделывание.

Ключевые слова. Вегетация озимой пшеницы, хранение зерна, виды пшеницы, механизм возделывания пшеницы.

INTRODUCTION

Wheat is one of the main food crops in Uzbekistan. It is considered a precious product for Uzbeks - it is used to make bread, because the national economic importance of grain is hard to ignore. The quality of bread products determines the grain content. Among other grains, winter wheat has a high protein content, which reaches up to 15% depending on the production technology and variety. In addition, grain is rich in carbohydrates and other important micronutrients.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The root system of winter wheat has a fibrous type. The branched root is located in the soil layer. Individual processes can reach a depth of up to 2 meters, depending on the characteristics of the crop. The primary root system is formed from three or even six roots formed from the embryo.

The stem is formed during the germination stage of the grain. It is called straw divided into several internodes that separate the stem nodes. The stem stops growing after the flowering phase is over. Photosynthesis, gas exchange and transpiration take place through the leaf surface. Leaves also temporarily store nutrients. An ear is the flowering of wheat. It consists of a stem and a spike. The latter has two glumes from which grains develop. Each grain has a seed (no more than 3% of the total weight of the grain). It and the husk are classified as bran. The duration of the vegetation period from the phase when winter wheat appears is on average 300 days.

RESULTS

Winter wheat varieties are hard and soft, their main difference is the degree of hardness. In addition, they differ in the content of starch and protein. And according to the quality characteristics, the classification of wheat is determined. Thus, six classes are recognized: - the first three classes (1, 2, 3) - cereals for food group A; - the next two (4 and 5) - grain for pasta products, non-food needs of group B; - the last class (6) - grain for feeding livestock - fodder. The classification of wheat quality indicators is different in different countries. There are no generally accepted standards in the world.

Varieties of durum wheat have a number of differences from soft wheat, including significant advantages, primarily production ones. Varietal features provide a stable vegetation of the crop. Durum wheat tolerates environmental influences better - pests and diseases affect crops less. Plants show high resistance to lodging, and the grain does not crumble. Under stable growing conditions, hard varieties show significant yields. Such wheat is popular in various sectors of the food industry: baking, flour-grinding, confectionery, pasta and others.

CONCLUSION

Planting winter wheat begins with the preparation of seeds, which are treated with protective agents against pests and diseases. It is planted in different ways: classic with a seeder, No-Till, Strip-Till, precise two-row, wide-row, etc. Winter wheat planting dates are determined according to the natural-climatic conditions and characteristics of the variety. The best period for Uzbekistan is September 20 - October 5. The germination of winter wheat planting is

significantly affected by the depth of the pit, which also determines the yield of the seedlings.

Harvesting of winter wheat is carried out in two ways: one-phase - direct combining and two-phase - separate. The first method is often used. Direct combining ears are used in clean fields with uniform ripening. After harvesting, the grain is immediately cleaned, dried and the necessary conditions for proper storage are created. Wheat is stored in a dry, well-aerated warehouse with a temperature of + 5-8 0C and a humidity of no more than 70%. Before placing the grain in the warehouse, it is disinfected to prevent the spread of diseases. To prevent spoilage of the grain mass, it must be constantly monitored.

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